

15/09/2025: Draft book chapter

WP5: Legitimate crisis governance and trust

Authors: Jakob Frateur, Loes Reijnders, Peter Bursens, Patricia Popelier

LEGITIMULT is a project funded by the European Union under Horizon Europe Programme, Call HORIZON-CL2-2021-DEMOCRACY-01, GA No 101061550.

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

Document information

CALL REFERENCE	HORIZON-CL2-2021-DEMOCRACY 01
PROPOSAL NUMBER	101061550
FULL TITLE	Legitimate Crisis Governance in Multilevel Systems
ACRONYM	LEGITIMULT
PROJECT START DATE	1 October 2022
PROJECT END DATE	30 September 2025

Document history

VERSION	DATE	DESCRIPTION	CONTRIBUTORS
1	15/09/2025	Draft book chapter	Jakob Frateur, Loes Reijnders, Peter Bursens, Patricia Popelier

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). Neither the European Union nor SERI can be held responsible for them.

LEGITIMULT is a project funded by the European Union under Horizon Europe Programme, Call HORIZON-CL2-2021-DEMOCRACY-01, GA No 101061550.

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

A citizens' perspective on crisis governance: trust in different government levels in times of crisis

Jakob Frateur, Loes Reijnders, Patricia Popelier, Peter Bursens

University of Antwerp, GOVTRUST Centre of Excellence

ABSTRACT

Research on crisis governance has shown that citizens' political trust is an important precondition for their compliance with crisis measures. However, little research has examined citizens' political trust in different levels of government during crises, despite the increasing involvement of subnational and supranational levels in the governance of crises. The COVID-19 pandemic presents an excellent example of a crisis that crossed sectoral and geographic boundaries, to which a response by various government levels was needed as shown in the SGEAI dataset. Especially in multilevel systems, a response from the national government alone cannot suffice. This chapter examines the variation in citizens' political trust across different levels of government in different types of multilevel systems when confronted with a crisis. The case countries are selected based on the findings of the SGEAI dataset. We selected two cooperative federal systems (Austria and Germany), characterized by weak decision-making power of the local level and stronger decision-making power, both direct and indirect through shared rule, of the regional Länder (especially in Germany); two competitive systems, one federal (Belgium) and one regionalized system (Spain) in which the local level obtained some decision-making power and in which the regional levels were strongly involved in decision-making; and two unitary systems (France and Netherlands) in which the local level obtained some decision-making power and in which subnational involvement in national decision-making was absent, but which differed regarding the autonomy of the regional level. We find, based on the analysis of unique survey data of 6000 respondents in six countries, that crises can (temporarily) boost political trust, and that the national level becomes more trusted during crisis situations while this is not consistently the case for other levels of government. This confirms earlier research on the rally effect but also shows that this effect might be limited to the national level only. Based on the SGEAI dataset, however, we also conclude that more research in intermediate government levels like (city) districts, metropolitan areas or provinces is necessary. While the SGEAI dataset shows that these levels were often heavily involved in crisis governance, systematic data on trust in these levels are lacking.

Jakob Frateur is a PhD student in the Department of Political Science, the Faculty of Law and the GOVTRUST Centre of Excellence at the University of Antwerp. He is researcher on LEGITIMULT Work Package 5 on Trust and Legitimate Crisis Governance.

Loes Reijnders is a PhD student in the Politics & Public Governance research group at the University of Antwerp. She recently joined LEGITIMULT and contributes to Work Package 5 on Trust and Legitimate Crisis Governance.

Patricia Popelier is professor of constitutional law at the Law Faculty of the University of Antwerp and the GOVTRUST Centre of Excellence. She is co-lead of LEGITIMULT Work Package 5 on Trust and Legitimate Crisis Governance.

Peter Bursens is professor of political science at the Faculty of Social Science of the University of Antwerp and the GOVTRUST Centre of Excellence. He is co-lead of LEGITIMULT Work Package 5 on Trust and Legitimate Crisis Governance.

INTRODUCTION

Political systems are becoming increasingly interconnected, establishing multilevel governance (MLG) structures. This means that local, regional, national and supranational levels of government each have their separate spheres of authority but also need to cooperate. This has made political systems increasingly complex (Behnke et al., 2019; Biela et al., 2013), which is especially evident in times of crisis. During the COVID-19 pandemic, for example, different levels of government were, in one way or another, involved in the mitigation of the crisis (Lynggaard et al., 2023). The SGEAI dataset reveals that in many European Union (EU) Member States subnational governments were, to different extents, engaged in the COVID-19 pandemic response. Citizens' perceptions of crisis governance were therefore not determined by actions of one level of government, but of a whole range of governments at different levels, each responsible for managing various aspects of the crisis.

This chapter discusses citizens' political trust in multiple government tiers in times of crisis. We examine how citizens' trust in governments at different levels varies when confronted with crisis-mitigating policies in multilevel systems. The multilevel approach to crisis governance in many countries underscores the importance of such a multilevel lens on political trust, itself an aspect of legitimate crisis response. Because of the various roles and competences of different levels during the crisis, we expect variation in citizens' trust between government levels, possibly correlating with different political systems, reflecting subnational levels' autonomy and shared rule.

Despite a growing body of research on crisis governance and citizens' trust, relatively little attention has been given to how citizens' trust varies across different levels of government, especially during crises that require coordinated multilevel responses. A differentiated analysis is warranted, since in most democracies (and particularly in the EU) competences for public health, economic support, and crisis response are shared and/or distributed across multiple levels of government, which are a fortiori involved in crisis governance. Trust is not only essential for the legitimacy of public institutions but also directly influences citizens' compliance with restrictive measures (Devine et al., 2024; Jennings et al., 2022), which is particularly important for crisis responses that rely on citizens' acceptance of and willingness to comply with pandemic measures and policies (Nielsen and Petersen, 2024).

The selected countries represent different types of political systems based on the findings of the SGEAI dataset. We opted for two cooperative federal systems (Austria and Germany), characterized by weak decision-making power of the local level and stronger decision-making power, both direct and through shared rule, of the regional *Länder* (especially in Germany); two competitive systems, one federal (Belgium) and one regionalized (Spain) in which the local level obtained some decision-making power and in which the regional levels were strongly involved in decision-making; and two unitary systems (France and the Netherlands) in which the local level obtained some decision-making power and in which subnational involvement in national decision-making was absent, but in which the authority of the regional level differed – strong in France, absent in the Netherlands. By analysing survey data from 6000 respondents across these six countries, we capture how trust in governments at

different levels varies both between and within systems of governance and how it changes in crisis scenarios. In doing so, this chapter contributes to literature on political trust, crisis governance, and MLG.

This chapter will first look at the literature on (political) trust: as a concept on its own and in relation to the concept of legitimacy, in the context of MLG, and during a crisis. Second, the six countries are used as cases for comparing trust in different levels of government during crisis and in non-crisis times. Finally, we look at the cases through a comparative lens.

POLITICAL TRUST

WHAT IS IT AND WHY IS IT IMPORTANT?

Political trust can be described as the belief of members of a political system that “political institutions will act consistently with their expectations of positive behaviour” (Algan, 2018). Political trust is thus characterized by a specific set of objects or trustees, namely political institutions, individual political actors or political systems (Zmerli and van der Meer, 2017). Furthermore, political trust is relational - in the sense that it entails a subject/trustor that trusts and an object/trustee that is trusted - and situational, meaning that it is characterized by a “certain degree of uncertainty about the object’s future actions” (Zmerli and van der Meer, 2017; Newton, 1999). This means that political trust is dependent on the actions of the object or the contexts in which the trust relation exists. As Hardin (2000) puts it, “A trusts B to do X”. In this chapter we study citizens’ (A) trust in governments at different levels (B) to take crisis response measures (X).

Political trust is often seen as a prerequisite of a successful government response to crises, given its association with compliance with crisis measures (Schraff, 2021; Bol et al., 2021). It is believed that political trust helps in maintaining stability, viability and legitimacy of the political system, and it is seen as a necessary precondition for democratic rule (e.g., Easton, 1975; Norris, 1999). In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, research showed that political trust was an important determinant of compliance with crisis measures, even the ones that affected fundamental rights (e.g., Caplanova et al., 2021; Siegrist et al., 2021). Furthermore, during the COVID-19 pandemic, low political trust was also linked to vaccine hesitancy (Wynen et al., 2022) and higher infection and mortality rates (Oksanen et al., 2020; Charron et al., 2023).

POLITICAL TRUST AND LEGITIMACY

Legitimacy and political trust are sometimes equated (e.g., O’Sullivan et al., 2014), while others study trust as an aspect of legitimacy (Grimes, 2006). Easton (1975), on the other hand, distinguished between political trust and political legitimacy by considering them as different types of political support. In his view, legitimacy refers to a normative judgment of political systems, related to norms and values, while trust implies an instrumental judgment on the regime’s performance (Easton 1975; Thomassen et al., 2017).

We consider trust and legitimacy as distinct but related concepts that share important features. While the object of legitimacy can be rather broad, including decisions and decision-making processes, the object of political trust is limited to political institutions like government(s), parliament, politicians, courts etc. Also, and contrary to legitimacy, trust cannot be perceived – there is no such thing as

perceived trust. More concretely, legitimacy refers to the general perception that a political institution is appropriate or rightful, whereas trust reflects the belief that the institution will act effectively in a specific context, such as governing, managing a crisis, or implementing particular measures.

At the same time, political trust and legitimacy also have many points of contact: drivers of the former are also central aspects of the latter, such as transparency and legality (e.g., Beetham, 2013; Hood and Heald, 2006; Boin et al., 2016). Moreover, citizens' political trust is considered a prerequisite of a successful government response to crises (Schraff, 2021) and of citizens' willingness to abide by government policies (e.g., Nielsen and Petersen, 2024; Devine et al., 2024; Jennings et al., 2022; Wynen et al., 2022; Bol et al., 2021). This way, political trust can also contribute to output legitimacy. Given these convergences, and the more concrete and measurable nature of trust, this chapter will concentrate on citizens' political trust to study a citizens' perspective on crisis governance.

POLITICAL TRUST IN A CONTEXT OF MULTILEVEL GOVERNANCE

Research shows that citizens, when evaluating political institutions and expressing political trust, differentiate between different actors and institutions at different levels of government (Proszowska et al., 2023; Angelucci and Vittori, 2023; Wolak, 2020; Fitzgerald and Wolak, 2016). However, this research is usually only concerned with two levels of government – most often national and supranational – paying little attention to subnational levels of government. Furthermore, research on political trust during the pandemic is mostly limited to studies of trust in the national level (Frateur, 2023), despite the involvement of multiple levels of government in the crisis response in many countries (Lynggaard et al., 2023; SGEAI dataset), and studies and datasets on trust mostly neglect regional levels (e.g., Eurobarometer surveys). The question, therefore, is whether and how citizens differentiate between levels of government – from the local to the supranational level – when confronted with a crisis.

When looking at trust in each level separately, it stands out that, at least in non-crisis times, the local (and regional) levels are generally trusted more than any other level (Wolak, 2020; Muñoz, 2017; Fitzgerald and Wolak, 2016) (although Stoker et al., (2023) show that this is not a global phenomenon (see, for example, China, Wu and Wilkes, 2018)). This higher trust in the local government is often explained by the typically smaller community size of lower government levels which can enhance the responsiveness of political institutions and actors, as well as foster direct contact with representatives (Muñoz, 2017). It also means that they are often more open to public participation. Additionally, the lower government levels have competences that influence citizens most directly. In sum, the proximity of these levels plays a substantive role in citizens' political trust (Stoker et al., 2023).

Regarding the supranational government levels, such as the EU, scholars argue that these are not necessarily less trusted than national government levels, even in times of crisis. The large size of higher levels of government is associated with more capacity and more policy output, relating trust to performance evaluations (Muñoz, 2017). Furthermore, research shows that in some cases, citizens express higher trust in supranational institutions to compensate for low trust in national institutions (e.g., Torcal, 2014; Armingeon and Ceka, 2014).

POLITICAL TRUST IN TIMES OF CRISIS

We use the COVID-19 pandemic as a case study to examine how the governance of a crisis impacts political trust. The pandemic is a ‘transboundary crisis’: a crisis that is not confined to specific locations, but affects citizens and/or systems beyond countries’ borders (Ansell et al., 2010; Boin, 2019), and one that can be an economic, political, health or social crisis at the same time, with a crisis in one domain impacting or even causing a crisis in other one(s) (Boin, 2019). The COVID-19 pandemic is a perfect example of a global crisis that started as a health crisis but quickly developed into a socio-economic (Guderjan et al. n.d.) and even political crisis. The disruptive, interconnected, and complex nature led to the crisis being dealt with by various levels of government, from the local to the supranational and even the global level.

Research has found an increase in trust at the onset of the pandemic (e.g., Weinberg, 2022; Schraff, 2021; Bol et al., 2021; van der Meer et al., 2023; Belchior and Teixeira, 2023). This temporary increase is most often attributed to a rally around the flag effect (e.g., Schraff, 2021; Weinberg, 2022; Esaiasson et al., 2021; van der Meer et al., 2023). There is, however, no agreement about whether this rally effect is a consequence of crisis-mitigating measures or the crisis itself. Some authors argue that the rally effect was driven by citizens’ appreciation of governments’ handling of the pandemic (e.g., Belchior and Teixeira, 2023; Bol et al., 2021), with citizens considering the implementation of far-reaching restrictions as responsive behaviour by governments. Others argue that it was an emotional response, driven by anxiety, to the threat and uncertainty caused by the spread of the virus which led citizens to pursue psychological safety behind political institutions (e.g., van der Meer et al., 2023; Schraff, 2021). Despite these different interpretations, the rally effect is generally accepted as a valuable explanation for the increase in trust, and believed to extend beyond institutions (directly) involved in crisis governance (Baekgaard et al., 2020; Esaiasson et al., 2021). This literature, with the notable exception of Biddle et al. (2024), is, however, largely limited to trust in the national government.

Research on trust in different levels of government during the sovereign debt crisis already showed the added value of an MLG perspective on political trust in times of crisis, despite the absence of a similar rally effect. As mentioned earlier, this literature mainly focused on the national and EU levels, but some studies also examine the broad category of ‘subnational levels’. These studies showed that trust in subnational levels of government – which were largely absent in terms of crisis governance – was higher than trust in the (supra)national level (Proszowska et al., 2022). This literature also finds that citizens differentiated between levels of government in times of crisis (Proszowska et al., 2023), but less than in the non-crisis situation (Talving and Vasilopoulo, 2021). Citizens thus differentiated between levels of government when making trust judgments in times of crisis, but the ratio of trust in different levels differs between crisis and non-crisis situations.

EMPIRICAL INSIGHTS ACROSS SIX EUROPEAN COUNTRIES

In this section, we first look at how different levels of government are part of the respective political systems and how they were involved in the COVID-19 crisis response, based on the SGAEI dataset. This overview shows that different levels of government were involved in the governance of the pandemic in different types of political systems, an observation that warrants the study of trust in the different levels of government.

We surveyed in six countries that differ in size, type of multilevel system and organization of crisis response: Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, the Netherlands and Spain (Frateur et al., 2024). These countries have been selected to provide a representation of different political systems (acknowledging that the countries are not fully representative of the EU, as Northern or Eastern European countries are not included). Participants were recruited through online panels and a sample of 1000 respondents per country, weighted based on age, gender and education through weighing methods employed by the survey company. As a result, we obtained a high-quality sample of 6000 respondents across six diverse countries.

The survey consisted of a set of survey questions and a hypothetical scenario based on and similar to the COVID-19 pandemic. This was deliberately chosen to increase realism and the recognizability for respondents. The scenarios, which were the same for each country, depicted a situation in which a deadly virus affected the respondent's country, and presented a policy reaction to the spread of the virus – a social restriction measure in the form of a lockdown and an economic support measure. This ties into the distinction between restriction and support measures that is often made in the literature and in datasets on pandemic management (SGEAI 20XX; Hale et al., 2021; Desvards-Larrives et al., 2020). Following this scenario, respondents had to answer several questions about their trust in various levels of government to take the measure. All respondents got both scenarios.

We study trust in the local, regional, national, and supranational levels, adjusted to the country of the respondent by asking 'how much do you trust the following government to take this [restrictive or support] measure', which was answered on a scale from 1 to 7. For practicality and comparability, we study only one local and one regional government per country – the ones most involved in pandemic governance – while the SGEAI dataset included all subnational tiers for each country. Using the scenarios, we can study the same citizens' perceptions and attitudes in non-crisis times and when faced with a (hypothetical) crisis, in our case, a pandemic.

In this section, we first discuss self-rule and shared rule of subnational levels during the COVID-19 crisis, and then look at citizens' trust in different levels of government in non-crisis times and when confronted with a crisis. In the discussion, we focus on citizens' trust in governments at different levels to take restrictive measures only, as the survey showed a strong correlation with trust to take economic support measures. Finally, we compare the results per type of system.

AUSTRIA

Austria is a cooperative federal system (Bussjäger and Schramek 2020). The Austrian political system is characterized by weak decision-making power of the local level and stronger decision-making power, both indirectly and through shared rule, of the regional level, i.e., the Länder. However, power is increasingly centralized from the Länder to the federal level (Bussjäger and Schramek 2020; Kössler, 2022).

The SGEAI dataset shows that the Länder increasingly gained authority through both self-rule and shared rule as the pandemic developed. They were regularly consulted in decision-making, at first mostly regarding restrictive measures, but later also regarding other policies, and had varying levels of autonomy throughout the pandemic. Municipalities did not have any decision-making authority, also not through shared rule, during the pandemic. The districts (Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde), composed

of groups of municipalities and an intermediate level between the local and regional levels, had some autonomy, though this decreased throughout the pandemic.

Figure 1: Differences in citizens' trust in government at different levels in the benchmark situation and when faced with a crisis in Austria ($p < .05$ indicated with *).

In the Austrian context, the survey classified the municipalities as the local level, and the Länder as the regional level. Trust in the districts was not measured separately. In the survey, Austrian respondents reported the highest level of trust in the local government in both non-crisis and crisis times (figure 1). Trust in the regional government level was lower, while the national and supranational governments were even less trusted. However, when respondents were confronted with a hypothetical crisis scenario, trust in the national government rose sharply, enough to surpass the supranational government, while the subnational governments remained the most trusted ones.

GERMANY

Similar to Austria, Germany is a cooperative federal system characterized by strong intergovernmental relations between the regional governments (Länder) and the federal government (Behnke 2023). The city districts (Kreise) and states (Länder) hold competences to adopt restrictive measures, while municipalities (Gemeinden) have no restriction competences.

The SGEAI dataset shows that, at the start of the pandemic, autonomy of the regional level was already at a relatively high level, and this autonomy remained high during the crisis. Their influence extended through a high level of shared rule as well, with meetings between the regional and the federal government leading to binding decisions. Local governments had no autonomy nor participated in decision-making at higher levels during the COVID-19 pandemic, despite the city districts' crisis management competences.

Figure 2: Differences in citizens' trust in government at different levels in the benchmark situation and when faced with a crisis in Germany ($p < .05$ indicated with *).

In the German context, the survey considered the municipalities as the local level, while the Kreise, an intermediate level between the local and regional levels, were not studied. The Länder were classified as the regional level. Germany showed a similar trend in trust in the different levels of government as Austria (figure 2). While trust in the local and regional levels did not significantly differ in a crisis compared to non-crisis times, trust in the national and supranational levels increased when confronted with a crisis. Trust in the national and the regional levels were more or less equally high during the crisis, while the local level remained the most trusted level in both scenarios.

BELGIUM

Belgium is a competitive federal system characterized by strong regional autonomy (Bursens et al. 2021). Unlike more cooperative federations, multiple levels of government have significant decision-making power but limited coordination mechanisms. None of the subnational government levels has general competences to take restrictive measures.

Based on the SGEAI dataset, we find that municipalities (gemeenten) and provinces (provincies) had some autonomy throughout the crisis, though this was relatively limited in scope. More substantial authority was concentrated at the regional level (Gewesten/Gemeenschappen), where the different governments played a larger role in the creation of policy through shared rule. National regulations allowed the municipalities and provinces to impose additional restrictions. The regions, in turn, had a medium to high level of autonomy, which included the competence to adopt restrictive measures within specific domains, e.g. in retirement homes (Popelier and Bursens, 2021), and which is consistent with the constitutional set-up of a competitive or dual federal system characterized by exclusive competences.

Figure 3: Differences in citizens' trust in government at different levels in the benchmark situation and when faced with a crisis in Belgium ($p < .05$ indicated with *).

In Belgium, the survey used the municipalities as the local level, while the Gewesten/Gemeenschappen were considered the regional level. The provinces, an intermediate level between the local and the regional level, were not included in the survey. The results reflected structural and institutional dynamics (figure 3). In non-crisis conditions, trust among Belgian respondents was highest in the local level, followed by the regional and supranational levels, with the national level being trusted the least. However, when presented with a crisis scenario, trust in the national level increased sharply, and the national level became the most trusted level. This shift indicates that, despite Belgium's decentralised system, citizens seem to turn towards the national government for crisis responses. Interestingly, the regional level was the least trusted during crises.

SPAIN

Spain is a competitive regionalized system (Léon et al. 2017) in which the local level has some decision-making power and in which the regional levels (Comunidades Autónomas) hold significant authority, but to varying degrees, and are limitedly involved in central decision-making. (Bossacoma Busquets & Sanjaume-Cabret 2019). Municipalities (Municipios) and provinces (Provincias) have no restriction competences.

Throughout the pandemic, the Autonomous Communities played a prominent role through shared rule with the federal level. Following the SGEAI dataset, they had a high shared rule score, meaning that joint meetings led to politically binding decisions. The Autonomous Communities also had some autonomy throughout the pandemic. In early 2022, the Autonomous Communities lost their shared rule competences, but their autonomy remained. Municipalities were also given some competences, but less than the regions, while the provinces had no form of autonomy throughout the pandemic and were not involved in shared rule.

Figure 4: Differences in citizens' trust in government at different levels in the benchmark situation and when faced with a crisis in Spain ($p < .05$ indicated with *).

The survey considered Spanish municipalities as the local level and Autonomous Communities as the regional level. The provinces, situated between the local and regional levels, were not surveyed. The survey data showed that both in a non-crisis situation and in a crisis situation, the EU was trusted the most (figure 4). This finding contradicts previous literature on lower levels being the most trusted (Wolak, 2020; Muñoz, 2017; Fitzgerald and Wolak, 2016). In non-crisis times, the local level was the second most trusted level, followed by the regional level, with the national level being the least trusted. When confronted with a crisis, trust in the national level rose the most, making the national level the second most trusted level. These results, also found in Belgium, suggest that even in a system where the regional level has substantial autonomy, citizens tend to turn toward the higher levels of government during times of uncertainty, possibly expecting a more unified and visible response.

FRANCE

France is a unitary system in which the local level holds some decision-making power, while subnational involvement in national decision-making is absent (du Boys et al. 2022). In times of crisis, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, the national government typically becomes the primary point of reference. None of the subnational levels, including the municipalities (Communes), metropolitan areas (Métropoles), departments (Départements), and regions (Régions) has competence to take restrictive measures.

The SGEAI dataset shows that, during the early stages of the COVID-19 crisis, all subnational levels were granted a moderate degree of autonomy through various decrees which stipulated that local governments could take additional measures based on local circumstances. Importantly, throughout the entire crisis, there was no form of shared rule. Subnational governments were not included in national-level decision-making processes, and no formal intergovernmental meetings took place.

Figure 5: Differences in citizens' trust in government at different levels in the benchmark situation and when faced with a crisis in France ($p < .05$ indicated with *).

In France there are four subnational government levels, but only two were surveyed. The municipalities were considered the local level. Metropolitan areas consist of different municipalities depending on the location and number of citizens, but not all municipalities belong to such an area, so this cannot be considered a uniform level of government. The survey opted to study the departments as the regional level, given that they were more involved in the pandemic than the regions (du Boys et al., 2022).

The survey data showed that during non-crisis times, French respondents trusted the local level the most (figure 5). Confronted with a crisis, however, trust in the local level declined and trust in the national level sharply increased, which means the national level changed from the least trusted in non-crisis times to the most trusted level in crisis. As France is a unitary system, most decisions were taken at the national level with minimal involvement of the regional level, yet the level of trust in the national level was similar to that of the other countries outside of crisis times. Contrary to the federal systems, trust in the regional level and trust in the local level were about the same in times of crisis, which may indicate the close connection between both levels.

THE NETHERLANDS

The Netherlands is also a unitary system (Wayenberg et al. 2022). This means that subnational levels are not involved in national decision-making and have very limited autonomy and competences. The municipalities (Gemeenten) in the Netherlands have the competence to adopt some restrictive measures, but the provinces (Provincies) have no restriction competences.

We observe, based on the SGEAI dataset, that, from the start of the pandemic in March 2020, various instructions by the Health Ministry granted municipalities a limited degree of autonomy. Municipalities were allowed to impose additional restrictions, provided these were already authorized by national legislation, and they could also grant exemptions to certain rules when appropriate.

Municipalities retained this moderate level of autonomy throughout the crisis. In contrast, provinces had no autonomy throughout the COVID-19 crisis. As in France, the Netherlands did not include subnational governments in national decision-making.

Figure 6: Differences in citizens' trust in government at different levels in the benchmark situation and when faced with a crisis in the Netherlands ($p < .05$ indicated with *).

In the Dutch survey, the municipalities are considered the local level, and the provinces as the regional level. In non-crisis times, Dutch citizens expressed most trust in the local level (figure 6), followed by the regional and supranational levels. The national level was the least trusted. This is very similar to almost all studied countries. Another common trend was that trust in the national level increased the most when looking at a crisis situation, surpassing the regional and supranational governments, but not the local government. The latter government is generally the most trusted, but differences in trust in the local level between crisis and non-crisis contexts are often negligible.

A COMPARATIVE PERSPECTIVE ON CITIZENS’ TRUST IN DIFFERENT GOVERNMENTS

Several trust patterns emerge across the six countries. In non-crisis times, trust generally followed a similar hierarchy: local governments were trusted the most, followed by regional, supranational, and finally national levels. This aligns with existing literature showing that proximity fosters trust (Wolak, 2020; Muñoz, 2017) and that the supranational level is not necessarily the least trusted one (Muñoz, 2017). An exception is Spain, where the EU was the most trusted level of government, both in and outside a crisis context.

Table 1: Differences in citizens' trust in government for different systems in a non-crisis situation and when faced with a crisis.

		Local	Regional	National	Supranational
Austria	Non-crisis	4.38	3.81	3.1	3.18
	Crisis	4.24	4	3.74	3.54
Germany	Non-crisis	4.55	4.1	3.52	3.49

	Crisis	4.51	4.17	4.17	3.95
Belgium	Non-crisis	4.2	3.82	3.51	3.57
	Crisis	4.32	4.2	4.54	4.26
Spain	Non-crisis	4	3.67	3.53	4.06
	Crisis	4.35	4.34	4.49	4.69
France	Non-crisis	4.59	4.23	3.38	3.43
	Crisis	4.35	4.22	4.56	4.11
Netherlands	Non-crisis	4.43	4.18	3.51	3.57
	Crisis	4.41	4.22	4.28	3.92

When confronted with a crisis (governance) scenario, trust in the national government and in the EU increased in all countries. This may reflect a rally effect, where trust increases at the onset of a crisis, particularly amongst citizens who express lower trust in government (van der Meer et al., 2023; Weinberg, 2022). However, the country analyses also show that trust in subnational levels of government did not consistently increase when confronted with a crisis. Trust in these levels often stayed the same or even decreased, which seems to indicate that a possible rally effect does not extend to lower levels of government but is limited to the national (and EU) levels (see also Biddle et al., 2024). Also, despite the often sharp increase in trust in crisis, the national government did not become the most trusted in all types of political systems (figure 7).

Figure 7: Differences in citizens' trust in government for different systems when faced with a crisis.

In unitary systems (France and the Netherlands), trust in the national government sharply increased in response to the crisis scenario. In France, the national level became the most trusted level during the crisis, while in the Netherlands, the local level remained the most trusted. Unitary systems often lack shared rule, meaning subnational governments have little to no role in national crisis decision-making. Despite centralization tendencies, trust in local government remains relatively high. Trust in the regional level holds less practical relevance since that level cannot typically make or implement crisis policy, unlike in federal and regionalized systems.

In cooperative federal systems (Austria and Germany), local and regional levels retained the highest trust, even during the crisis. While national-level trust rose, the continued high trust in subnational levels likely reflects the institutionalized collaboration and structural and predictable shared rule present in these systems. Despite the regional level being involved in federal decision-making, the highest level of trust remained in the local level.

Competitive systems (Belgium and Spain) showed a different dynamic. Despite strong regional autonomy, citizens in both countries shifted their trust toward the higher government levels during the crisis. In Belgium (a competitive federal system), national trust surpassed all other levels during the crisis, while in Spain (a competitive regionalized system), trust in the national level rose sharply but remained below trust in the EU. This may suggest that the absence of extensive coordination mechanisms between different government levels leads citizens to turn to higher levels for a uniform crisis response.

These comparative insights suggest that institutional structure and differentiation between levels of government matter when looking at trust. Federal systems with coordinated shared rule retained strong trust at subnational levels. In contrast, centralized unitary systems experienced a shift in trust toward national governments, possibly due to their visible leadership and resources. Competitive systems, despite autonomy at lower levels, showed a less strong increase in trust at lower levels during crises, at least compared to higher levels. Institutional structures therefore seem to be reflected in citizens' perceptions of and trust in their governments.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This chapter adds a MLG perspective to the literature on trust in times of crisis by studying, through an analysis of survey data of 6000 respondents in six diverse countries, how crisis governance affects trust in different levels of government. This chapter thereby addresses a gap in the literature that focuses mostly on trust in the national level of government in times of crisis, despite the involvement of governments at multiple levels in the governance of the crisis, as the SGEAI dataset shows.

This chapter's focus on political trust has provided an insight into how citizens regard different government levels in times of crisis. While citizens can perceive a political institution as legitimate (or not), political trust is a more instrumental evaluation of institutional performance in a specific context and, as such, can be considered an aspect of legitimacy. Citizens' political trust becomes especially important in times of crisis or uncertainty, when a crisis response relies on citizens' compliance with the measures. By examining how trust varies across government levels and crisis measures, this chapter offers a more detailed understanding of how political trust is evaluated under pressure, thereby also contributing to studies about the legitimacy of crisis governance.

The research yields two main findings that have some implications for further research and future crisis governance. Firstly, citizens express more trust in governments when faced with an emerging crisis than in a non-crisis situation. This increase may be attributed to a rally effect that is commonly used to explain the increase in trust at the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic and also seems to hold in an experimental research design that pictured the onset of a crisis. Faced with the uncertainty and threat of the crisis, citizens seek safety behind their governments and therefore increase their trust (Schraff, 2021; Bol et al., 2021; van der Meer et al., 2023). This may also explain why citizens' trust in different levels of government is less differentiated in times of crisis. It does not really matter who

takes the responsibility, it is more important that governments act when faced with a threat and related uncertainty. However, we consistently observe this increase in trust mainly for the national and EU levels. Trust in the local and regional levels stayed the same or even decreased in most of the studied countries, specifically in unitary and cooperative federal systems, when confronted with a crisis. So, the rally effect often observed in the literature but only tested for national government levels, seems to be limited to higher levels of government in these systems (as found by Biddle et al., 2024).

Second, following the literature on trust in multilevel systems, we also find that citizens differentiate between levels of government when expressing trust (Proszowska et al., 2023), but less so in times of crisis (see also Talving and Vasilopoulo 2021). In non-crisis times, the national government is trusted the least, not the supranational one. The common idea that, at least in Europe, subnational levels of government are trusted more than other levels of government (Muñoz, 2017; Stoker et al., 2023) seems to hold. However, turning to citizens' trust when faced with a crisis, the local level is not the single most trusted level, with trust in the national level increasing sharply in all countries. This seems to suggest that, when confronted with a crisis, perceptions of proximity and responsiveness of the subnational levels still play a role, especially regarding the local level (Muñoz, 2017; Proszowska et al., 2023), but also that the saliency and resources of the national level is relevant for citizens' trust judgments in crisis (Muñoz, 2017; Proszowska et al., 2022). It is important to note, however, that the local level is trusted similarly in crisis and non-crisis times.

The research contributes to the literature by focusing explicitly on trust in four levels of government (local, regional, national, and supranational levels) and by using an experimental scenario to obtain citizens' attitudes in times of crisis, which distinguishes the survey from other surveys that were fielded during a crisis itself. Our approach makes it possible to test changes in individual respondents' trust when they are faced with a crisis, and it allows us to test for the effect of crisis governance on citizens' trust. Our research also shows that the regional level cannot be neglected in research on trust (in crisis) and that it should be studied as a separate level instead of taken together with the local level as 'subnational levels', especially in multi-tiered systems. Finally, this research adds to the literature that uses the rally effect as explanation for trust evolutions during the pandemic by showing that the increase in trust seems to be limited to national and EU government levels.

Inevitably, there are also some limitations to the interpretation of our data and the results. First, we examined two subnational levels in each country, the local and the regional levels, but neglected intermediate levels of government like provinces in Belgium or Kreise in Germany. This improves comparability and generalizability, but it also means that we may have overlooked important variation in trust across different subnational tiers within countries. As a result, the data may not fully capture the nuance of within-country trust on different governance levels. The significant differences in trust between government levels highlight the importance of adopting an MLG perspective when studying political trust. Future research should therefore account for the subnational structures in each country.

Additionally, in interpreting our cross-system comparisons of trust across government levels, it is important to acknowledge that subnational levels, and especially what we call regional levels, differ substantially in their competences, autonomy, and involvement in shared rule. As a result, these levels are not fully comparable in practice. In unitary systems, where regional governments have very limited competences, trust in the regional level has less practical relevance for crisis governance and resembles more citizens' trust in the local level. By contrast, in federal systems, regional levels often have significant competences and thus more impact on crisis governance. Also, citizens in federal

systems express significantly different levels of trust in the regional level than in the local and national levels, indicating that citizens in these systems consider the regional level as a distinct level, while in unitary systems, this does not seem to be the case. This chapter, therefore, in a way, also points to the challenges of comparing regional levels with and without legislative competences, as they are also viewed differently by citizens.

Despite these limitations, our results contribute to the literature by showing the added value of an MLG perspective on trust in times of crisis. Especially because political trust is known to be a precondition for citizens' compliance with crisis-mitigating measures, citizens' trust needs to be sustained to make crisis governance work. By looking at the different levels, our research gives some indication as to which government is most trusted to take measures in the beginning of a crisis. While the rally effect is seen as an important explanation for the increase in trust in the beginning of the pandemic, this chapter shows that this increase in trust might be limited to (supra)national governments. This means that trust in subnational levels of government does not increase in the beginning of a crisis, despite the often higher level of trust in subnational governments in non-crisis times. As trust dynamics may differ between levels of government, future crisis governance may benefit from the interplay between various government levels instead of being hindered by it.

LITERATURE

- Algan, Y. (2018). Trust and social capital. In *For good measures. Advancing research on well-being metrics beyond GDP*. Paris: OECD Publishing, pp. 283-320.
- Angelucci, D., and Vittori, D. (2023). Where you live explains how much you trust local (and national) institutions: a study of the Italian case. *European Political Science Review*, 15(4), pp. 641-658.
- Ansell, C., Boin, A., & Keller, A. (2010). Managing transboundary crises: identifying the building blocks of an effective response system. *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*, 18(4), pp. 195–207.
- Armingeon, K., & Ceka, B. (2014). The loss of trust in the European Union during the great recession since 2007: the role of heuristics from the national political system. *European Union Politics*, 15(1), pp. 82–107.
- Baekgaard, M., Christensen, J., Madsen, J. K., & Mikkelsen, K. S. (2020). Rallying around the flag in times of Covid-19: societal lockdown and trust in democratic institutions. *Journal of Behavioral Public Administration*, 3(2), pp. 1–12.
- Beetham, D. (2013). *The legitimation of power* (2nd ed.). Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Behnke, N. (2023). Germany: cooperation and executive dominance. In LeCompte, K. *Teaching Federalism*. Edward Elgar Publishing, pp. 221-232.
- Behnke, N., Broschek, J., & Sonnicksen, J. (2019). *Configurations, Dynamics and Mechanisms of Multilevel Governance*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Belchior, A. M., & Teixeira, C. P. (2023). Determinants of political trust during the early months of the COVID-19 pandemic: putting policy performance into evidence. *Political Studies Review*, 21(1), pp. 82-98.
- Biddle, N., Gray, M., & McAllister, I. (2024). Federalism and confidence in Australian governments during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Publius: The Journal of Federalism*, 54(2), pp. 257–282.
- Biela, J., Kaiser, A., & Hennl, A. (2013). *Policy Making in Multilevel Systems: Federalism, Decentralisation, and Performance in the OECD Countries*. Colchester: ECPR Press.
- Boin, A., McConnell, A., & 't Hart, P. (2016). *Governing after Crisis: The Politics of Investigation, Accountability, and Learning*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Boin, A. (2019). The transboundary crisis: why we are unprepared for the road ahead. *Journal of Contingencies and Risk Management*, 27(1), pp. 94–99.
- Bol, D., Giani, M., Blais, A., & Loewen, P. J. (2021). The effect of COVID-19 lockdowns on political support: some good news for democracy? *European Journal of Political Research*, 60(2), pp. 497–505.

- Bossacoma Busquets, P. & Sanjaume-Calvet, M. (2019). Asymmetry as a Device for Equal Recognition and Reasonable Accommodation of Majority and Minority Nations. A Country Study on Constitutional Asymmetry in Spain. In Popelier, P. & Sahadzic, M. *Constitutional Asymmetry. Managing Multinationalism in Multi-tiered Systems*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 429-460.
- Bursens, P., Popelier, P., & Meier, P. (2021). Belgium's response to COVID-19: How to manage a pandemic in a competitive federal system? In Chattopadhyay, R. et al. *Federalism and the Response to COVID-19*. Routledge India, pp. 39-48.
- Bußjäger, P., & Schramek, C. (2020). Austria (Federal Republic of Austria) Balancing Distributed Federalism with Centralization. In Griffiths, A. et al. *The Forum of Federations Handbook of Federal Countries 2020*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 41-52.
- Caplanova, A., Sivak, R., & Szakadatova, E. (2021). Institutional trust and compliance with measures to fight COVID-19. *International Advances in Economic Research*, 27(1), pp. 47–60.
- Charron, N., Lapuente, V., & Rodriguez-Pose, A. (2023). Uncooperative society, uncooperative policies or both? Trust, polarization, populism and Covid-19 deaths across European regions. *European Journal of Political Research*, 62, pp. 781–805.
- Desvards-Larrive, A., Dervic, E., Haug, N., Niederkrotenthaler, T. et al. (2020). A structured open dataset of government interventions in response to COVID-19. *Scientific Data*, 7, pp. 285.
- Devine, D., Valgardsson, V., Smith, J., Jennings, W., Scotto di Vettimo, M., Bunting, H., & McKay, L. (2024). Political trust in the first year of the COVID-19 pandemic: a meta-analysis of 67 studies. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 31(3), pp. 657–649.
- du Boys, C., Bertolucci, M., & Fouchet, R. (2022). French intergovernmental relation during the Covid-19 crisis: between hyper centralism and local horizontal cooperation. *Local Government Studies*, 48(2), pp. 251–270.
- Easton D. (1975) A Re-Assessment of the Concept of Political Support. *British Journal of Political Science*, 5(4), pp. 435-457.
- Esaiasson, P., Sohlber, J., Ghersetti, M., & Johansson, B. (2021). How the coronavirus affects citizen trust in institutions and in unknown others: evidence from the ‘Swedish experiment.’ *European Journal of Political Research*, 60(3), pp. 748–760.
- Fitzgerald, J., and Wolak, J. (2016). The roots of trust in local government in western Europe. *International Political Science Review*, 37(1), pp. 230–146.
- Frateur, J. (2023). How multilevel governance structures and crisis mitigating measures impact political trust: a systematic literature review. *Perspectives on Federalisms*, 15(3), 55–85.
- Frateur, J., Corrado, S., Bursens, P., & Popelier, P. (2024). *POLTRUST in MLG* (Version 1.0). Zenodo.
- Grimes M. (2006). Organizing consent: The role of procedural fairness in political trust and compliance. *European Journal of Political Research*, 45(1), pp. 285-315.

Guderjan, M., Herrero Alcalde, A., Kölling, M. & Schnabel, J. (n.d.). Crisis governance, economic policies and social welfare: what effects does MLG have? Chapter 7 in this book.

Hale, T., Angrist, N., Goldszmidt, R., Kira, B., et al. (2021). A global panel database of pandemic policies (Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker). *Nature Human Behaviour*, 5(4), pp. 529–538.

Hardin, R. (2000). Do we want trust in government? In Warren, M.E. (ed.). *Democracy and trust*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 22-41.

Hood, C., & Heald, D. (2006). *Transparency: the key to better crisis governance?* Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Jennings, W., Stoker, G., Valgarðsson, V., Devine, D., and Gaskell, J. (2021). How trust, mistrust and distrust shape the governance of the COVID-19 crisis. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 28(8), pp. 1174–1196.

Kössler, K. (2022). Managing the Covid-19 pandemic in Austria: from national unity to a de facto unitary state? In Steytler, N., *Comparative federalism and Covid-19. Combating the pandemic*. London: Routledge, pp. 70-87.

León, S., Mota, F. & Salvador, M (2017). The Organization of Spain: Ideology, Territory and Representation in the State of Autonomies. In *Political Power in Spain: The Multiple Divides Between MPs and Citizens*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 245-264.

Lynggaard, K., Jensen, M. D., and Kluth, M. (Eds.). (2023). *Governments' Responses to the Covid-19 Pandemic in Europe*. Cham: Palgrave MacMillan.

Muñoz, J. (2017). Political trust and multilevel government. In Zmeri, S. and van der Meer, T. *Handbook on political trust*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing, pp. 69-88.

Newton K. (1999). Social and political trust in established democracies. In Norris, P., *Critical Citizens. Global support for democratic government*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 169-187.

Nielsen, L. H., & Petersen, M. B. (2024). Beyond left and right: The role of system trust in COVID-19 attitudes and behaviours across eight western countries. *European Journal of Political Research*, pp. 1-12.

Norris P. (1999). *Critical Citizens. Global Support for Democratic Governance*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Oksanen, A., Kaakinen, M., Latikka, R., Savolainen, I., Savela, N., & Koivula, A. (2020). Regulation and trust: 3 month follow-up study on Covid-19 mortality in 25 European countries. *JMIR Public Health and Surveillance*, 6(2).

O'Sullivan, S., Healy, A. E., and Breen, M. J. (2014). Political legitimacy in Ireland during economic crisis: insights from the European social survey. *Irish Political Studies*, 29(4), pp. 547–572.

Popelier, P., & Bursens, P. (2022). Managing the Covid-19 crisis in a divided Belgian federation: Cooperation against all odds. In Steytler, N. (ed.). *Comparative federalism and Covid-19. Combating the pandemic*. London: Routledge, pp. 88–105.

Proszowska, D., Denters, B., & Jansen, G. (2023). Political trust in a multilevel polity: patterns of differentiation among more and less politically sophisticated citizens. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 89(1), pp. 165-185.

Proszowska, D., Jansen, G., and Denters, B. (2022). On their own turf? The level-specificity of political trust in multilevel political systems. *Acta Politica*, 57, pp. 510–528.

Schraff, D. (2021). Political trust during the COVID-19 pandemic: rally around the flag or lockdown effects? *European Journal of Political Research*, 60(4), pp. 1007-1017.

SGEAI dataset

Siegrist, M., Luchsinger, L., & Bearth, A. (2021). The impact of trust and risk perception on the acceptance of measures to reduce COVID-19 cases. *Risk Analysis*, 41(5), pp. 787–800.

Stoker, G., Bunting, H., & McKay, L. (2023). Trust and local government: a positive relationship? In Teles, F. (ed.). *Local and Regional Governance*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing, pp. 49-64.

Talving, L., & Vasilopoulo, S. (2021). Linking two levels of governance: citizens' trust in domestic and European institutions over time. *Electoral Studies*, 70, pp. 1–15.

Thomassen J., Andeweg, R. and Van Ham, C. (2017). Political trust and the decline of legitimacy debate: a theoretical and empirical investigation into their interrelationship. In Zmerli, S. and van der Meer, T. (eds.). *Handbook on political trust*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing, pp. 509-525.

Torcal, M. (2014). The decline of political trust in Spain and Portugal: economic performance or political responsiveness? *American Behavioral Scientist*, 58(12), pp. 1542–1567.

van der Meer, T., Steenvoorden, E., & Ouattara, E. (2023). Fear and the Covid-19 rally around the flag: a panel study on political trust. *West European Politics*, 46(6), pp. 1089-1105.

Wayenberg, E., Resodihardjo, S. L., Voets, J., Van Genuchten, M., Van Haelter, B., & Torfs, I. (2022). The Belgian and Dutch response to Covid-19: change and stability in the mayors' position. *Local Government Studies*, 48(2), 271–290.

Weinberg, J. (2022). Trust, governance, and the Covid-19 pandemic: an explainer using longitudinal data from the United Kingdom. *The Political Quarterly*, 93(2), pp. 316–325.

Wolak, J. (2020). Why do people trust their state government? *State Politics & Policy Quarterly*, 20(3), pp. 313–329.

Wu, C., and Wilkes, R. (2018). Local-national political trust patterns: why China is an exception. *International Political Science Review*, 39(4), pp. 436–454.

Wynen, J., Op de Beeck, S., Verhoest, K., Glavina, M., Six, F., Van Damme, P., Beutels, P., Hendrickx, G., & Pepermans, K. (2022). Taking a COVID-19 Vaccine or Not? Do Trust in Government and Trust in Experts Help Us to Understand Vaccination Intention? *Administration and Society*, 54(10), pp. 1875–1901.

Zmerli, S., & van der Meer, T. (2017). *Handbook on political trust*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing.